

SOME APPLICATIONS OF ALMOST HERMITIAN METRIC PSEUDO f –MANIFOLDS ON WALKER 4 –MANIFOLDS

Sibel TURANLI¹

ORCID: 0000-0001-6747-6757

sibel.turanli@erzurum.edu.tr

Elif ÇETİNKAYA²

ORCID: 0000-0000-0000-0000

elif.cetinkaya14@erzurum.edu.tr

Çağrı KARAMAN³

ORCID: 0000-0001-6532-6317

cagri.karaman@atauni.edu.tr

¹ Faculty of Science, Department of Mathematics, Erzurum Technical University, Erzurum, Türkiye

² Faculty of Science, Department of Mathematics, Erzurum Technical University, Erzurum, Türkiye

³ Faculty of Science, Department of Mathematics, Atatürk University, Erzurum, Türkiye

*Yazışılan müellif: sibel.turanli@erzurum.edu.tr ; Tel.: +90-546-5296548

ABSTRACT

In this study, properties of almost Hermitian metric pseudo f – structures are investigated on 4 – dimensional Walker manifolds (M_4, g) and the necessary and sufficient condition for the integrability of these structures is obtained. The necessary and sufficient condition is obtained for the triple (M_4, f, g^W) to be a Hermitian metric pseudo f – Kähler Walker manifold. The Riemannian curvature tensor R^W , Ricci tensor Ric^W and scalar curvature s^W of the Walker 4 – manifold (M_4, f, g^W) based on almost Hermitian metric pseudo f – structure are calculated.

Keywords: Hermitian metric, f –structure, Walker manifold, Curvature tensor, Ricci tensor.

REFERENCES

1. Davidov, J., Diaz-Ramos, J. C., Garcia-Rio, E., Matsushita, Y., Muskarov, O., Vazquez-Lorenzo, R. 2007. Almost Kähler Walker 4-manifolds. Journal of Geometry and Physics, 57(3), 1075-1088.

2. Davidov, J., Diaz-Ramos, J. C., Garcia-Rio, E., Matsushita, Y., Muskarov, O., Vazquez-Lorenzo, R. 2008. Hermitian–Walker 4-Manifolds. *Journal of Geometry and Physics*, 58(3), 307-323.
3. Kon, M., Yano, K. 1985. Structures on manifolds. Series in pure Mathematics, World Scientific, (3).
4. Matsumoto, K. 1976. On a Structure defined by a tensor field f of type $(1, 1)$ satisfying $f^3 - f = 0$. *Bulletin of Yamagata University. Natural science*, 9(1), 33-46.
5. Matsushita, Y. 2005. Walker 4-manifolds with proper almost complex structures. *Journal of Geometry and Physics*, 55(4), 385-398.
6. Salimov, A. A., Iscan, M., Turanli, S. 2011. Differential geometry of Walker manifolds. *Ученые записки Казанского университета. Серия Физико-математические науки*, 153(3), 264-271.
7. Walker, A. G. 1950. Canonical form for a Riemannian Space with a parallel field of null planes. *The Quarterly Journal of Mathematics*, 1(1), 69-79.